

Fertilizer management – organic sources

Effect of sesbania, rice straw, and pre-incubation on urea hydrolysis in wetland soil

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Interest in using leguminous green manure (LGM) crops has increased in the face of high costs of chemical fertilizers and growing concern for maintaining long-term soil productivity and ecological sustainability. Short-duration LGM crops can be inserted into intensified cropping systems, for incorporation before the main crop. The large amounts of residue from high-yielding cultivars also are being burned or incorporated. LGM crops or crop residues usually are allowed to decompose for different lengths of time before the main crop is sown with N fertilizer application.

The transformation of applied N may be influenced by incorporated LGM crops and crop residues. We studied the effect of incorporating sesbania and rice straw residue, and the length of decomposition, on urea hydrolysis in a wetland soil.

Experimental soil was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.1, EC 0.16 dS/m, 0.34% organic C, 0.06% N, and CEC 8.3 meq/100 g. Ten-g soil samples were treated with 0.2% sesbania green manure and 0.5% rice straw (dry weight

basis). The soil samples were submerged and incubated at $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 1, 7, and 14 d. After incubation, soil samples were treated with a urea solution at 200 $\mu\text{g N/g}$ soil.

Two samples from each treatment were taken 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h after urea application and extracted with 2 M KCl containing 5 μg phenylmercuric acetate (PMA)/milliliter. Urea concentrations in the KCl-PMA extract were determined by the diacetyl monoxime method.

Urea hydrolysis proceeded more rapidly in soil treated with rice straw than in soil treated with sesbania. It increased with higher concentrations of amend-

ments and with longer periods of incubation.

Urea hydrolysis was calculated as

$$\ln(a-x) = \ln(a) - Kt$$

where a = initial concentration of urea-N, x = decrease in urea-N concentration up to time t , and K = specific rate constant.

Plots of the logarithm of concentration of urea left unhydrolyzed against time t showed linear relationships, indicating that, irrespective of sesbania and rice straw treatment, urea hydrolysis followed first order kinetics. The average time for half the hydrolysis to occur ($t_{1/2}$) varied from 0.37 to 1.86 d; the reaction coefficient for the soil varied from 0.373 to 1.875/d (see table). ■

Regression equations of $\log(a-x)$ (Y) versus time (X), R^2 , reaction-coefficient (K), and $t_{1/2}$ for soil treated with sesbania and rice straw.

Soil treatment ^a	Regression equation	R^2	K (day ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (d)
<i>1-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.43 - .024X$	0.955	0.373	1.86
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 2.37 - .027X$	0.956	0.504	1.38
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 2.25 - .017X$	0.662	0.447	1.55
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 2.32 - .031X$	0.904	0.639	1.09
<i>7-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.35 - .035X$	0.932	0.732	0.95
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 2.40 - .036X$	0.989	0.746	0.93
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 2.27 - .033X$	0.916	0.777	0.89
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 1.19 - .026X$	0.699	1.131	0.61
<i>14-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.05 - .029X$	0.794	1.009	0.69
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 1.93 - .027X$	0.622	1.217	0.57
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 1.75 - .025X$	0.536	1.468	0.47
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 1.53 - .019X$	0.565	1.875	0.37

^aLGM = leguminous green manure (sesbania), RS = rice straw.

Multiplication of azolla associated with rice

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Multiplication of azolla is limited by several constraints. We studied producing inoculum in a part of a ricefield for multiplication as an intercrop. On the day rice was transplanted, an area 25 m² of 225-m² plots was fenced with a coconut cord tied with *Aeschynomene*

stems (to make the cord buoyant on the floodwater). The wet season experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with four treatments and three replications.

Plot A: Half of 250 g single super-phosphate (SSP), 10 g carbofuran (CF), and 10 g phorate-10-G (Ph) was spread on the fenced area (the additional inputs were kept in the middle of the plot in three open polythene bags).

Plot B: Half of 500 g SSP, 20 g CF, and 20 g Ph were applied the same way as in Plot A.

Plots C and D: control for plots A and B, respectively. The additional SSP was applied at 7-d intervals, the additional CF at 16 d after transplanting when insect infestation on azolla occurred. No insecticide was applied to the rice.

Twenty kg fresh biomass of azolla hybrid (IRRI strain No. 4030) was used as inoculum in plots A and B. Half the azolla present in plots A and B was harvested at 4-d intervals and inoculated to plots C and D.

Azolla biomass production was high, with no remarkable difference between